

Unsupervised generative chord representation learning and its effect on novelty-creativity and fidelity-standards

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Abstract

Generative models in deep learning have experienced great development in art generation. Even though image-based art generation has had a big success, music still needs to catch up compared to its visual counterpart. Extreme focus on improving the generated outputs has neglected the importance of understanding what generative models learn and understand about music. This investigation aims to understand how latent space characteristics can be related to the concepts of creativity, fidelity, and novelty. Unsupervised variational autoencoders (VAEs) with different latent space characteristics were trained to generate chords. Reconstruction and generation capabilities were analyzed. A set of probing networks was trained to determine the representations learned by the unsupervised models. Particular focus was drawn to identify which musical concepts were learned in the latent space. Analysis shows that a bigger latent space will favor, with limitations, *novelty-creativity* at the expense of *fidelity-standards*, which gets worse but also to a limit. Other findings show that smaller latent spaces do not allow for good dataset reconstruction but still follow good *fidelity-standards* at generation time at the expense of lower *novelty-creativity*. Finally, results show that bigger latent spaces are required for learning complex musical concepts.

1 Introduction

Throughout the centuries, new technologies have influenced the way humans create art. The invention of cameras changed how painted art was created, audio synthesis and processing revolutionized how music is created and listened to. Nowadays, artificial intelligence is one of the fastest-growing technologies affecting human creation. In particular, generative models have been among the newest revolutions in the arts field.

¹<http://creativai-uc.github.io>

Although visual art and music generation with deep learning have improved throughout the years, the focus has been on obtaining good results on the generated art without diving into the underlying mechanisms of what machines learn and understand about art and how it correlates to human-created musical features. These mechanisms are particularly interesting in unsupervised generative models that have to create their representations of art concepts without labeled examples.

This work aims to move forward in the direction of understanding what unsupervised generative models learn about music, which concepts these models learn, and how those concepts are represented in the latent space, utilizing a profound statistical analysis based on PCA and latent space probing. There is evidence that statistical models, even with limited data and chord choices, can outperform models based on Hidden Markov models such as the one by Schulze and van der Merwe (2011), considered for many years the state-of-the-art, and uncover patterns resembling established music theory concepts (Tsushima et al., 2018). This work seeks to contribute to the explainability of music representation learning with unsupervised generative models. We hypothesize that in generative models, larger latent spaces will favor *novelty-creativity* over *fidelity-standards*, and smaller latent spaces will favor *fidelity-standards* over *novelty-creativity*.

2 Latent spaces in generative models

Generative models in machine learning describe how data is generated in terms of a probabilistic model $p_{model}(x)$. Generative models are trained to mimic the unknown distribution of the data $p_{data}(x)$. It is possible to generate new data by sampling from $p_{model}(x)$. The model is considered a success if: (1) the model can generate examples that appear to have been drawn from $p_{data}(x)$ and (2) the model can generate examples that are suitably different from the observations of the training dataset (Foster, 2019). (1) and (2) are the key elements for evaluating the quality of a generative model.

2.1 Novelty & Fidelity

In AI, *novelty-creativity* refers to the ability of a system to generate new and surprising ideas, concepts, or outputs that depart from existing solutions. This involves pushing the boundaries of what is considered possible while maintaining coherence and relevance. On the other hand, *fidelity-standards* represent the established norms, expectations, or constraints within a specific domain. An AI system demonstrating high fidelity adheres to these standards, producing outputs that align with pre-existing rules and conventions. Striking a balance between these two concepts is crucial: excessive novelty without grounding in standards might lead to nonsensical outputs, while strict adherence to standards might stifle creativity and limit exploration. The ideal AI system navigates this tension, generating fresh ideas that respect the domain's existing framework.

On the one hand, it is possible to say that the ability of the model to generate examples that appear to have been drawn from $p_{data}(x)$ is related to the concept of *fidelity*. On the other hand, it is possible to say that the ability of the model to generate examples that are different from the training dataset is related to the concept of *novelty*. It is always important to optimize both *fidelity* and *novelty* and not one over the other.

2.2 Representation Learning: Latent Spaces

The main challenge of generative models is to sample high-dimensional data from a distribution that resembles the training dataset. Deep learning excels in dealing with the problem of finding structures in high-dimensional and highly correlated data. Deep learning can learn representations or features in a low-dimensional space that captures the essence of the high-dimensional data. Furthermore, these features or representations are not hard-coded but are trained and learned by the model. This ability of deep learning is a form of *representation learning*. The idea is to create a low-dimensional *latent space* that represents some high-dimensional data and a mapping function that can take a point of the *latent space* and to a point in the original domain.

2.3 Probing Classification

Latent spaces of unsupervised generative models are a low-dimensional representation of data that contain features for generating new examples. Probing classifiers, are small neural networks used to evaluate the quality of the models' representations (Conneau et al., 2018). These probes are small neural networks trained to classify specific features of the generated example directly from the latent space. If the classifier succeeds, it means that the generative model stores the information about the feature in latent space. Furthermore, probes are agnostic with respect to the models' architecture. Even though there are some problems in determining the parameters that allow a probe to be called a success (Belinkov, 2022), control tasks (Hewitt and Liang, 2019) help establish better conclusions by comparing the performance of a probe trained with real data and random noise (Conneau et al., 2018) (Zhang and Bowman, 2018) (Tenney et al., 2019). This allows discarding that the probe is just memorizing the data. Probing classifiers have been used mainly in linguistic tasks but also in music (Conneau et al., 2018) (Thoret et al., 2021) (Shi et al., 2016) (Adi et al., 2016).

3 Methodology

3.1 Chords: the chosen examples

Chords have a significant amount of musical information and have the advantage that they can be simplified by eliminating the temporal dimension. We have chosen to represent chords in a sparse vector notation, where each vector entry represents a note, and the value of the entry represents the dynamic, with *forte* being 1, *mezzoforte* $2/3$, *piano* $1/3$, and no sound 0. This allows for a simpler representation that is easier to deal with for machine learning models. Chords can be created and studied using well-established musical rules and it is also possible to scale the level of complexity of the chords according to the number of notes present and the intervals used.

3.2 VAE: the chosen generative model

Variational Auto-Encoders (VAEs) have a latent space from where to sample new examples and can be used as unsupervised generative models and have been proven to be useful for the generation of chord sequences (Comanducci et al., 2023). VAEs are simple models that can be easily trained without much hyperparameter exploration. Also, with VAEs is possible to both encode and decode data from the latent space. With this capability, it is possible to analyze the generation of new chords and the reconstruction of existing ones. Indeed, VAEs can learn disentangled representations that align with timbre spaces. For this work, it was decided to train VAE models with 4, 8, 16, and 32 latent dimensions and test how these changes affected the results.

3.3 Dataset

A dataset was created for the experiments ². This dataset contains four sub-datasets: the Triad Training Dataset, the Triad Validation Dataset, the Tetrad Validation Dataset, and the Random Validation Dataset, summarized in table 1.

3.3.1 Triad Training Dataset and Triad Validation Dataset

This dataset contains 1.080 triad examples. Each example is a 45-d vector where each vector entry represents a single note ranging from C on the first octave to Ab on the fourth octave. The value of the vector entry represents the dynamics of that note.

There are ten triad types in this dataset: major, minor, and diminished in root, first and second inversion, and augmented triads. There are examples of all the triad types with all the 12 available notes of the Western musical system across 3 octaves for a total of 36 base notes. The vector has 45 entries because when the base note is Bb in the third octave (36th entry), in the worst case (major triad second inversion or diminished triad first inversion), the third note is an Ab₄ (45th entry). Finally, each example was created with three different dynamics: *forte*, *mezzoforte*, and *piano*. This gives a total of $10 * 12 * 3 * 3 = 1,080$ examples. 90% (972) were randomly selected as the Triad Training

²Dataset is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7030289>

Dataset, and the remaining 10% (108) examples were assigned to the Triad Validation Dataset. The Triad Training dataset is the only one presented to the models during training.

Data augmentation is needed for the Triad Training Dataset since the number of examples is relatively small and could lead to over-fitting. For each of the 972 examples, 1,000 additional examples were created by adding random Gaussian noise ($\mu = 0, \sigma = 1/36$) to each vector entry for a total of 972,000 training examples. Adding Gaussian noise creates diverse, realistic variations of existing data, enriching the dataset and forcing models to learn underlying patterns instead of memorizing specifics.

3.3.2 Tetrad Validation Dataset

The Tetrad Validation Dataset contains 792 examples of tetrads. Each example is a basic seventh-chord tetrad. There are eight seventh chord types in this dataset: augmented major seventh, major seventh, minor major seventh, augmented seventh, dominant seventh, minor seventh, half-diminished seventh, and diminished seventh. Each of these tetrads was recorded with 33 base notes, ranging from C in the first octave to A in the third octave. Finally, each example was created with three different dynamics. This gives a total of $8 * 33 * 3 = 792$ examples. This validation dataset aims to test whether the model can also generalize the learning from the Triad Training Dataset to chords that have four notes and are a simple extension of the triad concepts, as tetrads build upon triads by adding another third interval.

3.3.3 Random Validation Dataset

The Random Validation Dataset was constructed by generating one thousand examples of three random notes out of the 45 possible notes. Each example is saved on the three possible different dynamics for a total of 3,000 examples. The objective of this validation dataset is to test whether the model is memorizing the input and copying to the output or learning the musical structure of the chords.

Table 1: Datasets Summary.

Name	Type	Num. Examples	Num. Notes	Description
Triad	Training	972	3	triads
Triad	Validation	108	3	triads
Tetrad	Validation	792	4	7th chords
Random	Validation	3000	3	rand. pitches

3.4 Model Architecture

The model is a single-input, single-output fully-connected Variational Auto Encoder (VAE). The encoder has a (None, 45) dimensional input tensor. Then, one Dense hidden layer with batch normalization, ReLU activation and dropout. The hidden layer goes to two output Dense layers without linear activation. One dense layer outputs the mean (μ) tensor of the VAE, and the other the logarithmic variance ($logvar$) tensor of the VAE.

The sampler takes a random tensor from a $\sim Normal(\vec{\mu} = 0, \vec{\sigma} = 1)$ distribution and adjusts it according to μ and $logvar$ from the encoder output. The result is the output tensor \vec{z} that is the latent tensor that represents the decoder input in the latent space.

The decoder takes the output of the sampler as input to one Dense hidden layer with Batch normalization and ReLU activation. The hidden layer tensor is fed to one last output layer with by Sigmoid activation since the output has to be between 0 and 1.

3.5 Training Method

The reconstruction loss defined in equation 1 is used so the model outputs the same thing that was given at the input. The Kullback-Leibler Divergence Loss (kl_{loss}) defined in equation 2 is used to generate a continuous latent space that follows a Gaussian distribution. The total loss is a weighted sum of the two losses as shown in equation 3.

$$r_{loss} = \frac{1}{N} \sum^n (Y - \tilde{Y})^2 \quad (1)$$

$$kl_{loss} = -0.5 \cdot \sum (1 + \log var - \mu^2 - \exp^{\log var}) \quad (2)$$

$$Loss = kl_{loss} + r_{loss_factor} \cdot r_{loss} \quad (3)$$

Adam is used as the optimizer for the model with a learning rate of $\alpha = 3 \cdot 10^{-5}$. The models were trained for 20,000 epochs. At that point, no more significant improvement in validation was observed. The model with the best performance on the validation dataset was saved for analysis.

4 Results, Analysis, and Discussion

4.1 Reconstruction Results and Analysis

4.1.1 PCA Analysis of datasets and trained models.

An analysis of the amount of information encoded from the data into latent space and its distribution is useful since VAEs have an encoder that compresses data and a decoder that decompresses it to the original representation. PCA analysis Jolliffe (2002) of the latent space of the validation dataset results in figure 1. Top-left graph shows that the model with four latent dimensions has variance evenly distributed across each component. The same is true for the model with eight dimensions (top-right). Models with 16 and 32 latent dimensions (bottom) only 9-10 components contain information.

Figure 1: PCA Analysis of Validation Datasets.

From the analysis, the optimal encoding rate for triads is from 45 dimensions to 9-10 latent dimensions. However, for less latent dimensions, the model always decodes triads but not all the possible triads, enforcing the hypothesis that fewer latent dimensions favor *fidelity-standards* but diminish *novelty-creativity*. Nevertheless, more than ten latent dimensions do not seem to improve *novelty-creativity* nor decrease *fidelity-standards* in a significant way.

4.1.2 Reconstruction and KL-Divergence Losses Comparison

It is possible to compare the reconstruction loss and the KL-divergence loss between the different models and across the three validation datasets. Table 2 contains the KL divergence losses, and table 3 contains the reconstruction losses of the models.

KL-Divergence loss penalizes the latent space to differ much from a Gaussian distribution. We should expect a higher KL-divergence loss on the tetrad dataset since the latent space needs to capture more features and a lower KL-divergence loss in the random validation dataset. This is exactly what is shown in table 2. It is also possible to notice that KL-divergence loss increases with the number of latent dimensions, meaning that more features are captured favoring *novelty-creativity*.

Table 2: Trained Models KL-Divergence Losses.

Latent Dim	4	8	16	32
Triad Validation	9.50	10.64	10.61	11.27
Tetrad Validation	9.89	11.13	11.20	11.94
Random Validation	8.65	10.13	10.25	10.83

Table 3 shows that the reconstruction loss of the random validation dataset is orders of magnitude greater than the triad validation dataset, meaning that the model can not reconstruct random data and it is not memorizing. Also, the reconstruction loss decreases from four to eight latent dimensions, meaning that four dimensions are insufficient to reconstruct, sacrificing *novelty-creativity* but maintaining *fidelity-standards*.

Table 3: Trained Models Reconstruction Losses.

Latent Dim	4	8	16	32
Triad Validation	0.101	0.055	0.042	0.066
Tetrad Validation	1.077	0.496	0.451	0.423
Random Validation	1.480	1.207	1.188	1.141

4.1.3 Note Only Reconstruction Analysis

Reconstruction loss is not the best metric to tell whether the right notes were reconstructed. It is not that important that the model is slightly off in the continuous value of a note as long as the notes played at the input are the same at the output.

Tables 4 and 5 contains the reconstruction accuracy and precision, respectively. All models have almost perfect accuracy and precision. Even though the four-latent dimensions model has fewer dimensions than recommended by the PCA analysis, it still performs almost as good as the other models, reinforcing that less latent dimensions can still maintain *fidelity-standards*.

Table 4: Note Only Reconstruction Accuracy.

Latent Dim	4	8	16	32
Triad Validation	0.998	1.000	1.000	1.000
Tetrad Validation	0.948	0.980	0.985	0.985
Random Validation	0.920	0.935	0.937	0.940

Table 5: Note Only Reconstruction Precision.

Latent Dim	4	8	16	32
Triad Validation	0.997	1.000	1.000	1.000
Tetrad Validation	0.761	0.946	0.953	0.949
Random Validation	0.361	0.517	0.537	0.577

4.1.4 Triads latent space distribution and nearest neighbor analysis

There are different ways that all the triads can be ordered in a latent space for it to be smooth and continuous. Table 6 shows the average number of notes in common of a triad and its nearest neighbor,

its second nearest neighbor, and so on. It is possible to see that, on average, the nearest neighbor of a triad has more than two notes in common and that that number decreases as triads get further apart on the latent space meaning that triads are arranged by notes in common.

Table 6: Average notes in common with nearest neighbors.

Dim	N0	N1	N2	N3	N4	N5
32	2.64	2.37	2.05	2.02	1.95	1.94
16	2.63	2.35	2.03	2.00	1.93	1.92
8	2.58	2.31	2.05	2.00	1.93	1.93
4	2.00	2.00	1.92	1.84	1.74	1.65

4.1.5 Tetrads latent space distribution

It is essential to understand how the models can reconstruct and generate tetrads even though they have never seen one during training. Tetrads can be constructed either stacking another musical third over a triad, or by combining two triad chords. Table 7 repeats the neighbor analysis. It looks for the average number of notes in common of a tetrad with its nearest triad neighbors. It is possible to conclude that tetrads are next to the triads that have the notes that compose them, but are tetrads an extension of a triad or a combination of two triads?

Table 7: Average notes in common tetrad with triad nearest neighbors.

Dim	N0	N1	N2	N3	N4	N5
32	2.87	2.77	2.52	2.40	2.29	2.20
16	2.80	2.72	2.51	2.43	2.25	2.18
8	2.80	2.71	2.47	2.38	2.21	2.29
4	2.26	2.07	1.97	1.94	1.82	1.76

By observing the distance of a tetrad to the triads that compose them, it is possible to understand in which way tetrads are formed. If tetrads are in the middle of the two similar triads that compose them, it means that tetrads originate from the interpolation of two triads in the latent space. Equation 4 allows determining which option is correct. α quantifies how evenly a generated tetrad lies between two constituent triads in latent space; values close to zero indicate balanced interpolation. Thus, an α value closer to 0 means that tetrads are in the middle, and an α value closer to 1 means that tetrads are closer to one particular triad.

$$\alpha = \frac{|dist_1 - dist_2|}{dist_1 + dist_2} \tag{4}$$

$$dist_i = \|\vec{tetrad} - \vec{triad}_i\|$$

Table 8: Mean α value of tetrads.

Dim	α
32	0.125
16	0.146
8	0.212
4	0.126

The results of this analysis are in table 8. It is possible to conclude that, on average, tetrads are in the middle of the triads that compose them. This means that tetrads are an interpolation of triads in the latent space, or in other words, *novelty-creativity* surges from interpolation in the latent space of already known examples.

4.2 Generation Results and Analysis

The following experiment’s characterize the generation patterns of the trained models and contrast them to the training dataset characteristics. All the experiments were done by sampling one million

random normal ($\mu = 0, \sigma = 1$) points and passing them through the model’s decoder to generate the examples.

4.2.1 Generated notes histogram analysis

The first experiment consists of analyzing the distribution of the generated notes. Figure 2 shows the distribution of notes of the training dataset and the distribution of generated notes by the model. The models learned the underlying distribution of notes of the training dataset and followed the same rules for generating new examples.

Figure 2: Generated notes histogram.

4.2.2 Number of notes generated per chord analysis

Figure 3 shows the distribution of the number of notes per chord generated by the trained models. The dataset only contains chords of three notes, but the models also generate chords with two, four, five, and more notes, with the distribution spreading out as the number of latent dimensions increases. This shows that less latent dimensions allow for better *novelty-creativity* at the cost of poorer *fidelity-standards*.

4.2.3 Dynamic generated histogram analysis

The third experiment analyzes the distribution of the dynamics of the generated chords. The training dataset has chords in which all the notes always have the same dynamic. Figure 4 shows three graphs.

The upper-left graph, shows the proportion of times a single note is active on each of the three dynamics. It is possible to note two things. First, generated notes tend to be of a more quiet dynamic (*piano*) than a louder dynamic (*forte*). This can be explained by considering that in the dataset, for each example, only three of the 45 notes have a value greater than 0, implying that each note is more probably inactive than active. Second, as the number of latent dimensions decreases, this bias towards *piano* notes is decreased, confirming the idea that fewer latent dimensions improve *fidelity-standards* in the models.

The lower graph shows the proportion of chords having one, two, or three different dynamics. Models do not follow the dataset rule of generating chords with all the notes at the same dynamic. Even though the model should follow the dataset distribution this problem is also a good feature since it increases variability and creativity.

The upper-right graph shows the proportion of times a chord contains a note with each dynamic. Chords tend to have notes with different dynamics with a preference to *piano* notes.

Figure 3: Number of notes per chord generated histogram.

Figure 4: Dynamics histogram.

4.2.4 Intervals generated histogram analysis

The fourth experiment analyzes the distribution of the generated chords' intervals. All dataset triads are constructed by stacking major and minor thirds. Considering that the dataset also contains the inversions of the chords, some notes can be separated by five or six semitones. Figure 5 shows the distribution of intervals of the dataset in solid gray columns and the distribution of intervals of the trained models.

Trained models generate a significant proportion of minor and major second intervals. All models produce the same proportion of the minor second interval but different proportions of the major second interval. Neighbor chords in latent space have the most notes in common, so the minor second interval probably appears because, for most triad types, the difference between one type and another is just a semitone in one note. The major second interval appearance is probably due to a similar effect.

From figure 5, it is possible to note that if outlier intervals are ignored, the generated intervals follow the same proportions as the training dataset. This is a clear sign that the model learned the underlying distribution of the training dataset.

Figure 5: Intervals histogram.

4.3 Latent Space Probes Results and Analysis

The last analysis to perform is to understand what information is contained in the latent space of the models. A great tool to use for this purpose are probing classifiers. If a probe can classify the category or concept directly from the latent space, it means that that information is present inside the latent space.

Seven probes were trained. Each probe tries to classify a different musical concept directly from the latent space. All probes were trained with real data from the models and fake random data as a control experiment. The real data probe not only needs to outperform random chance but also the ability of the random data network to memorize the correct answers directly. All probes were trained with one million examples (90%-10% training-validation data split), for 2 thousand epochs with categorical cross-entropy loss and Adam optimizer.

4.3.1 Triad type probe with inversions

This probe tries to classify the triad type that a point in latent space will generate. Table 9 contains the validation accuracy of the real and fake dataset probes. By random chance, the probe should have an accuracy of 0.1. The random dataset probe slightly improves from random chance showing that the probe does not memorize data. The real dataset probe has twice the accuracy of random chance, and the 32 latent dimension probe is almost three times better than random chance. This means that the latent space contains information about the triad type.

4.3.2 Triad type probe without inversions

This probe tries to classify the triad type that a point in latent space will generate, but this time without regard to the inversion. There are only four valid categories: major, minor, diminished, and augmented. This probe aims to determine whether the latent space understands inversions as

Table 9: Triad type with inversions probe results.

Dim	Real	Fake
	Accuracy	Accuracy
32	0.279	0.117
16	0.214	0.133
8	0.200	0.120
4	0.205	0.121

variations of the same chord category or if it learns each inversion of a chord as a completely different structure. Table 10 contains the validation accuracy and loss of the real and fake dataset probes.

Table 10: Triad type without inversions probe results.

Dim	Real	Fake
	Accuracy	Accuracy
32	0.400	0.304
16	0.351	0.331
8	0.361	0.318
4	0.362	0.345

By random chance, the probe should have an accuracy of 0.25. The random dataset probe improves from random chance. However, this time the improvement of the real dataset probe over the fake dataset probe is insignificant, with the 32 latent dimensions model having a noticeable improvement over lower latent dimensions models. With these results, it is possible to say that the models' latent spaces learned the ten types of triad structures as separate categories.

4.3.3 Single note probe

The following three probes tries to classify each individual note present in a triad. for each probe there are 45 possible categories. Table 11 contains the validation accuracy and loss of the real and fake dataset probes for the base note, the second note and the third note of the triads. The real dataset probes perform with excellent accuracy, with all probes over 96%. This means that the information about each individual note of a triad is present in the latent space.

If these results are compared with sections Triad type probe with inversions and Triad type probe without inversions results, it is possible to say that the models generate three note chords by individually selecting the notes without a clear notion of structure or relationship between them. All models can learn the notes that generate a triad. However, only higher latent dimension notes can encode the structure of the chord.

Table 11: Single note probe results.

Dim	Base Note		Second Note		Third Note	
	Real Acc.	Fake Acc.	Real Acc.	Fake Acc.	Real Acc.	Fake Acc.
32	0.973	0.045	0.969	0.052	0.978	0.042
16	0.977	0.041	0.955	0.038	0.983	0.040
8	0.976	0.041	0.960	0.044	0.982	0.052
4	0.965	0.043	0.944	0.046	0.974	0.046

4.3.4 Dynamic probe

This probe tries to classify the dynamic of the generated triad that a point in latent space will generate. Table 12 contains the validation accuracy and loss of the real and fake dataset probes. By random chance, the probe should have an accuracy of 0.33. Results show that the random dataset probes are better than random chance with a 50% accuracy. Nevertheless, the real probes have an accuracy of over 68% percent, showing that there is information about the dynamic of a chord in the latent space, but it is unclear. The 32 latent dimensions probe performs much better than the other probes.

Table 12: Dynamic probe results.

Dim	Real Accuracy	Fake Accuracy
32	0.750	0.500
16	0.681	0.515
8	0.683	0.500
4	0.691	0.538

5 Conclusions and future work

Our analysis explores dimensionality reduction in music representation using PCA. While 10 dimensions suffice for faithful reconstruction, fewer dimensions remain useful for identifying musical elements like chords. Interestingly, the latent space organizes chords by shared notes, with dynamically diverse chords spaced farther apart. When exploring novelty and creativity, more dimensions in the latent space enable the generation of novel tetrads based on triads while adhering to established chord structures. Finally, increasing dimensions capture more features, allowing models to accurately represent notes, octaves, and, to a lesser extent, triad type and dynamics.

Figure 6: Conclusions summarized in one abstract graph (own elaboration).

In summary: (1) reconstruction increases with latent dimensions until the PCA threshold, (2) *fidelity-standards* are maintained high when latent dimensions decrease below the PCA threshold and do not get much worse over the PCA threshold, (3) *novelty-creativity* increases with latent dimensions, but with a ceiling not far over the PCA threshold, and (4) musical concepts learning increases when latent dimensions are way higher than the PCA threshold. All this can be seen in one conclusive and abstract picture shown in figure 6. To conclude, we have shown that larger latent spaces will favor *novelty-creativity* over *fidelity-standards* and smaller latent spaces will favor *fidelity-standards* over *novelty-creativity*.

One possible future work to explore is combining this work with (Macaya et al., 2020) and creating models that can directly generate chords in audio and sparse vector formats. A multi-modal architecture can combine audio representations with sparse vector representations and generate latent spaces that could capture more features and learn better representations of music. Inspiration can be drawn from OpenAI’s CLIP model that combines text with image generation (Bianchi et al., 2024). Combining sparse vector representation with audio will help analyze whether the results of this work, which uses only sparse vector notation, are replicable to models that use audio representations.

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